

CREATING LEVERAGE TO ENHANCE BIODIVERSITY OUTCOMES
OF GLOBAL BIOMASS TRADE

Application of new Biodiversity indicators

Deliverable 2.5

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Executive summary

In this deliverable, we demonstrate how the previously developed biodiversity indicators (D2.2-4) can be applied towards answering diverse and pressing research questions relevant to biodiversity science. Specifically, we apply these indicators towards improving understanding of the impacts of different environmental drivers (and their interactions (sections M1,R1)), as well as towards improving understanding of human-impacts on biodiversity (section M2, R2).

First, we conducted a study assessing how much biodiversity (measured as a composite index of richness, endemism, and phylodiversity, among other indicators) might be lost under different future scenarios – and the extent to which different environmental drivers (land-use, fire recurrence, and climate) play a role in this loss. We found significant biodiversity losses across tropical regions under both optimistic and pessimistic policy-scenarios. Moreover, while predictions show significant losses will occur even under scenarios with moderate climate policies (more optimistic), the differences between policy-scenarios are particularly substantial in the Amazon region. Thus, we show how – despite likely biodiversity losses across the tropics by 2050 – choosing to enact policies to curb GHG emissions can still have a large impact in mitigating future biodiversity loss in biodiversity-rich regions.

Second, we illustrate how these indicators could be used to further understanding of human-influence on biodiversity patterns by focusing on the case of land tenure in Brazil. Here, we collate parcel-level data on land ownership/registration and pair these data with the biodiversity data (richness, endemism). We conduct a spatial overlay analysis and identify which categories of land ownership (private lands, rural settlements, protected areas and indigenous lands) hold higher/lower biodiversity in their properties/lands. We found that private lands have higher biodiversity (richness and endemism) per property-km² than all other tenure categories. We also paired information on the vegetation surplus and deficit (i.e., the land-cover requirements of Brazil’s Forest Code) in private lands and rural settlements to highlight: 1) how the Pantanal and the Cerrado/Caatinga biomes are currently conserving biodiversity, and 2) how the highest potential biodiversity gains through restoration are along the arc of deforestation. We argue that, in some regions, private landholders need lasting incentives to continue conserving biodiversity in places with currently high levels of conservation. By contrast, in other regions such as the Amazon, they need improved incentives to comply with the law’s restoration requirements.

Overall, sound and targeted conservation policies and strategies are contingent upon region-specific information about biodiversity, drivers of biodiversity loss, and integrated strategies that consider the complexities of multiple interacting factors. In this deliverable, we highlight actionable insights through the application of biodiversity indicators we have developed as a part of CLEVER. Moreover, the work presented in this deliverable demonstrates how CLEVER research on trade-specific impacts may connect across broader research agendas, and contribute towards more effective policies and governance strategies for biodiversity conservation overall.

Introduction

The global biodiversity crisis is a critical sustainability challenge, with profound implications for both ecosystem functioning and human well-being^{1,2}. On the one hand, the primary and often interrelated drivers of biodiversity loss include land/sea-use-change, direct exploitation, climate change, invasive alien species, and pollution^{3,4}. These threats are amplified by interactions between land-use change, climate change, and fire⁵⁻⁷. On the other hand, the underlying drivers of this loss are often linked to socioeconomic factors, including the (poor) governance of natural resources – though these are often more difficult to evaluate because in addition to being difficult to isolate interacting effects, acquiring data at biodiversity-relevant scales is also challenging. Against this background, understanding the drivers of the biodiversity crisis in detail, and being able to apply currently available biodiversity data and knowledge to characterize these drivers remains an urgent research frontier.

Various research efforts investigate global biodiversity loss and its drivers using a variety of approaches and methods⁷⁻²⁵. Notwithstanding these efforts, several limitations persist. First, current research seldom addresses interactions between key drivers, and in particular, the role of fire – despite evidence of its growing impacts⁵. Thereby, current predictions of global biodiversity patterns likely underestimate biodiversity losses^{18,20-22,25}. Second, studies that use habitat integrity as a proxy to estimate biodiversity loss generally focus on land-use changes and predominantly rely on vertebrates due to the greater availability of geospatial data^{8-13,21-23}. As a result, these approaches often overlook plants and, above all, invertebrates, both of which play fundamental ecological roles^{26,27}. Recent evidence of strong declines in invertebrate populations underscores the need to include a greater diversity of taxonomic groups to enhance the breadth and accuracy of biodiversity impact assessments²⁸⁻³⁰. Third, most studies typically use a single biodiversity metric³¹, providing only a partial view of the multiple dimensions of biodiversity which may skew perceptions of the loss/persistence of certain species^{9,11,20}. Fourth, many models use polygonal data drawn by experts^{8-11,13,19,21,32}, which have been key for species distribution modeling (SDMs); however, may not accurately represent species distributions, as they are often affected by sampling biases and data gaps, particularly in tropical regions where data availability is often limited.^{33-35 13,22,23,25}

Finally, though many studies increasingly focus on the human drivers of biodiversity loss³⁶⁻³⁹, the scales at which socioeconomic data are available often do not match those of biodiversity data⁴⁰⁻⁴². That is, while biodiversity patterns are typically described at relatively fine spatial grains (e.g., at 1km² pixels), socioeconomic factors such as demography, income, or technology, are typically available either at specific locations (one field site), or at higher administrative levels (e.g., municipalities, states, or country-levels). Examining biodiversity patterns across a small number of field sites fails to capture broader trends, whereas aggregating biodiversity data at large administrative levels can blur the influence of local management decisions. Hence, conducting analyses where biodiversity-specific indicators are applied towards understanding the influence of human drivers at management-relevant spatial scales remains elusive.

In this deliverable, we aim to improve upon several of these limitations in understanding both environmental and human drivers by applying the previously developed biodiversity indicators (**D2.2-4**) towards two different research questions (**Objectives**). Across both research questions, we capture multiple dimensions of biodiversity including species

richness, endemism, and phylogenetic diversity (alongside other factors, see **M1**), as well as integrate biodiversity data from many taxa and classes (**M1**). In answering the first research question on environmental drivers, we test how climate, land-use, and fire interact to influence future biodiversity scenarios (**M1**, **R1**). Here, using different policy scenarios, we aim capture the impact that tailored national and regional policies can have in curbing biodiversity loss across the tropics. In answering the second research question, we use a unique parcel-level dataset on land-tenure in Brazil, to investigate the association between a specific human driver – land tenure – across Brazil’s different regions and ecosystems (**M2**). In this section, we capture the influence of land tenure as a mediating factor influencing local land-use decision-making, as property rights – i.e., rights of use, extraction, management, or exclusion – are inherently determined by different categories of land tenure.

Through these improvements, advanced modeling methods, and overall new applications of biodiversity indicators, we provide new evidence for the influence of environmental and human drivers of biodiversity – and what this means for current and future effective conservation strategies.

Objectives

The main objective of this deliverable is to apply the newly developed biodiversity indicators to assess the influence of specific environmental and human drivers on biodiversity across the tropics. Specifically, we aim to answer the following research questions:

- 1) How do different environmental drivers (climate, land-use, and fire) influence future biodiversity patterns?
- 2) How are current biodiversity patterns distributed across different land-tenure categories in Brazil?

Methods

In this section we describe the methods used in two subsections corresponding to the two outlined research questions, **M1** (on the influence of environmental drivers), and **M2** (on the influence of land-tenure regimes as a human driver).

Both research questions apply the biodiversity indicators developed throughout **D2.2-4**, species richness, endemism, and phylogenetic diversity. As previously described, these metrics, represent complementary aspects of biodiversity, and were derived using species occurrence data from GBIF (as described in D1.1-3), which were cleaned and processed to ensure taxonomic and spatial accuracy. To address spatial sampling biases, the methodology incorporated explicit consideration of sampling effort, following the principles established in previous deliverables.

M1. Influence of environmental drivers: Future impacts of land-use, climate, and fire on biodiversity scenarios across the tropics

Here, we outline the methods behind investigating how climate, land-use, and fire influence future biodiversity patterns under different policy scenarios. To this end, we use the previously described biodiversity indicators and summarize them into an index. We choose two different future scenarios and apply advanced modeling techniques to project biodiversity patterns to the year 2050 under these scenarios. Additionally, we analyze how these key drivers—land-use change, climate, and fire—interact and differentially influence biodiversity loss across regions. By disentangling their relative contributions, we identify areas where specific drivers dominate and where synergistic effects amplify biodiversity decline, allowing for a more targeted approach to conservation and mitigation strategies.

Application of biodiversity indicators: PCA of biodiversity variables

Aiming to improve upon the common practice of using a single biodiversity metric, we applied a Principal Component Analysis (PCA) to integrate multiple biodiversity dimensions into a composite representation. This approach allows us to retain the multidimensional nature of biodiversity while reducing redundancy among five biodiversity metrics: species richness, species composition, endemism, phylogenetic diversity, and phylo-endemism. Instead of oversimplifying biodiversity into a single measure, PCA enables us to identify dominant biodiversity gradients while preserving the unique contributions of each metric. The first principal component (PC1) explained 63% of the variance across the metrics, effectively capturing key biodiversity patterns at a regional scale. By summarizing biodiversity in this way, we ensure that complex spatial patterns remain interpretable without disregarding the importance of individual biodiversity components.

Projecting future biodiversity scenarios

To evaluate biodiversity under future scenarios, we used the Shared Socioeconomic Pathways SSP2-4.5 and SSP5-8.5, representing policy scenarios where GHG emissions are moderate and high, respectively. The SSP framework was developed by the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) to explore different trajectories of global development, emissions, and climate change. These pathways provide

standardized socioeconomic and emission scenarios, allowing for comparisons across studies and ensuring consistency in climate impact assessments. SSP2-4.5 represents a middle-of-the-road scenario where economic growth and environmental policies follow historical trends, leading to moderate emissions and climate impacts. In contrast, SSP5-8.5 describes a fossil-fuel-intensive scenario, where economic expansion drives high emissions, resulting in stronger climate change effects⁴³. We selected these two pathways because they capture a range of plausible future conditions, enabling us to assess biodiversity responses under both moderate and extreme climate scenarios and guide conservation planning accordingly.

To project biodiversity patterns into 2050, we integrated these SSP scenarios into our models by incorporating future climate projections, land-use change trajectories, and fire recurrence models. The climate projections were derived from three general circulation models (HadGEM3-GC31-LL, MIROC6, and MPI-ESM1-2-HR), each downscaled to a regional resolution. These were then fed into biodiversity models trained with current climate, land-use, and habitat index data, allowing us to estimate species richness, endemism, phylogenetic diversity, and species composition under future conditions. Additionally, fire recurrence models were developed based on historical patterns and projected into 2050 under each SSP scenario. By integrating these environmental drivers, we were able to quantify biodiversity loss at a global scale, estimate the relative contribution of each driver, and identify regions at higher risk, supporting more effective conservation strategies.

Impacts of environmental drivers and their interactions

To assess the relative contributions of environmental drivers on biodiversity loss, land-use data, fire recurrence, and climatic variables (temperature and precipitation) were integrated into the modeling framework. This integration was achieved by incorporating these variables as key predictors in a spatially explicit biodiversity model, which estimates species richness, composition, endemism, phylogenetic diversity, and phylo-endemism across different scenarios. The model captures how these environmental factors shape biodiversity patterns over time, allowing for a comprehensive evaluation of their individual and combined effects.

To isolate and disentangle the specific impacts of land-use change, climate, and fire, we applied a jackknife resampling technique, systematically running models where each driver was held constant while others varied. By comparing these controlled scenarios to the fully integrated model, we quantified the independent effect of each factor on biodiversity loss. Additionally, we used a cluster analysis based on multidimensional Euclidean distance to classify regions according to their dominant drivers of biodiversity decline. This approach allowed us to determine whether biodiversity loss in a given region was primarily driven by land-use change, climate change, fire, or a combination of these factors, providing insights into how these stressors interact across different ecosystems.

M2. Influence of land tenure as a driver of biodiversity patterns in Brazil

Here, we paired up-to-date, parcel-level land tenure data and biodiversity models of species richness and endemism in order to link the distribution of biodiversity across the different tenure categories in Brazil. We focus on Brazil as a case study within CLEVER, as Brazil's rural environmental cadaster provides a globally unique record of land registries which in total covers over 80% of land in Brazil. By contrast, such spatially-detailed data on land tenure is not publicly available across other tropical countries – or is typically limited to few categories such as protected areas. Additionally, we connected this information with estimated property-level deficits in the natural vegetation for compliance with Brazil's Forest Code, to provide further direction for future conservation and restoration priorities through fuller compliance with existing policy infrastructure.

Application of Biodiversity data

We used the previously developed biodiversity indicators (**D2.2-4**), focusing on species richness and endemism. Though we initially included phylogenetic diversity in our analyses, results were redundant with those for richness in all cases, therefore we decided to exclude the metric from the analyses described here. While the models were trained using tropics-wide data (i.e., including observations for the entire South America, Africa, and Southeast Asia), they were projected to Brazil for this specific study.

As a result, we used species richness (here, the average number of species potentially found in a grid cell of approximately 1 km²), and endemism (here, the sum of the inverse of species-specific areas of distribution found in a grid cell of approximately 1 km²). Hence, the endemism values in the analysis weigh rarer species more highly, as these might be more at risk for extinction than more common species. Given these data are at approximately a 1 km² resolution, our findings are only applicable to properties ≥1 km². Thus, our analysis is not directly applicable to smaller farms which may also play critical roles for biodiversity conservation due to likely higher diversity on smaller farms⁴⁴.

Land tenure data compilation

Here, we compiled land tenure data from a variety of sources (**Table 1, Fig. 2A**), cleaning spatial errors and resolving overlaps within categories, and identified areas of overlaps across categories. By contrast to previous compilations⁴⁵ these data have not undergone a hierarchization process to resolve data overlaps across different tenure categories, which can be subject to different interpretations of how categories should be prioritized. Instead, we quantified current overlaps across categories (which we find to be approximately 1.4 million km², or around 18% of all registered areas); and conducted spatial overlays of biodiversity separately for each of these categories⁴⁶.

Table 1. Categorization and sources of land tenure data. Total area is rounded to the nearest 100th km², and mean/min/max exclude properties <1km² as this was most relevant to subsequent analyses.

Category	Area (km ²)	Mean area (km ²) (min/max)	Source
Private lands / rural properties (<i>imóveis rurais</i>)	4,836,400	5 (1 - 26,896)	Centro de Sensoriamento Remoto (CSR), Imaflora,
Rural settlements (<i>assentamentos rurais</i>)	307,800	37.3 (1 - 8,642)	Serviço Florestal Brasileiro
Strictly protected areas (<i>unidades de conservação de proteção integral</i>)	487,000	802 (1 - 41,871)	
Sustainable use protected areas (<i>unidades de conservação de uso sustentável</i>)	574,200	2,107 (1 - 36,045) 2,197 (1 - 85,297)	Ministerio do Meio Ambiente, 2023
Indigenous lands	1,023,500		FUNAI, 2023
Quilombola lands	29,800	84 (1 - 7,198)	INCRA, 2023
Undesignated lands	670,000	426 (1 - 15,955)	SFB, 2021

Property-level deficit for complying with Brazil's Forest Code

Connecting to previously carried out work at UFMG (on estimations of the carbon-sequestration potential of fuller compliance with Brazil's Forest Code (FC)⁴⁷), we also wanted to estimate what the biodiversity restoration potential of fuller FC compliance might look like. The FC legally requires property owners to maintain a certain percentage of land under natural vegetation; 80% in the Amazon biome, 35% in the Cerrado portions in the legal Amazon, and 20% in remaining biomes. The FC also includes specific provisions for deforestation that occurred before 2008 and has specific stipulations for *reservas legais* and *áreas de preservação permanente*, which are areas of conservation within rural private lands. Part of the stipulations for properties with deforestation pre-2008 include a requirement to restore vegetation to comply with these percentages – yet, compliance for this restoration requirement remains low⁴⁸. Following all these stipulations and requirements, the team at UFMG updated the 2020 estimates on the amount of native vegetation in “surplus” as well as in “deficit” across all private lands and rural settlements in Brazil in 2023 (**Fig 3A**)^{47,49}.

We used these updated estimates – paired with the biodiversity data – to map current richness and endemism in properties with surplus (i.e., remnants of vegetation that exceed the FC minimum requirements; **Fig 3B**), identifying areas where private properties already support biodiversity conservation. Then, to identify restoration potential, we used additional layers of our biodiversity models that estimate species richness and endemism without land-use-based human-intervention to illustrate “potential” biodiversity (**D2.2 – D2.4**). We took the difference between these estimates of “potential” and “current” biodiversity, and further weighed this difference by the total deficit of properties' vegetation requirements for FC compliance (**Fig 2B**). Hence, we identified areas where properties' fuller compliance with FC restoration requirements may lead to highest gains in biodiversity.

Results & Discussion

R1. Influence of environmental drivers: Future impacts of land-use, climate, and fire on biodiversity scenarios across the tropics

Future biodiversity loss under different scenarios

The results reveal significant biodiversity losses across the tropical regions by 2050 under both SSP2-4.5 (moderate emissions) and SSP5-8.5 (high emissions) scenarios (**Figure 1 b-e**). Biodiversity loss was quantified using a single index derived from the first Principal Component of a PCA, which explained 63% of the variation across multiple dimensions of biodiversity (**Figure 1a**). This integrated approach allowed for a comprehensive assessment of biodiversity declines, highlighting spatial patterns and the magnitude of losses across the study regions.

In **South America**, the Amazon Basin emerges as the most critically affected region, with 77% of its extent projected to experience significant biodiversity losses. Under SSP2-4.5, the average relative decline in biodiversity in this biome reaches 10% (**Figure 1b**), increasing to 26% under SSP5-8.5 (**Figure 1d**). The Pantanal and Chaco regions also show considerable biodiversity losses, with relative declines of up to 10% and 26% under SSP2-4.5 and SSP5-8.5, respectively. These losses are especially concerning given the high ecological value and unique biotas these areas support.

Significant biodiversity losses are projected across tropical regions of South America, Africa, and Asia, with some areas losing up to 30% of their biodiversity by 2050 under SSP5-8.5. In Africa, **the Congo Basin** exhibits biodiversity losses comparable to those in the Amazon, reaching 30% in some regions. Montane ecosystems, such as the Albertine Rift, are particularly vulnerable, with losses reaching 12% under high-emission scenarios. The Southern African savannas and ecotone regions also face significant declines, with relative losses of 5% under SSP2-4.5 and increasing to 9% under SSP5-8.5, threatening not only biodiversity but also ecological and socioeconomic systems.

In South America, absolute biodiversity loss is expected to reach up to 30% in the Amazon, Chaco, and Pantanal under SSP2-4.5 (**Figure 1c**), with losses increasing by an additional 17% under SSP5-8.5 (**Figure 1f**). In Southeast Asia, particularly in Indonesia and the Mekong Basin, biodiversity decline is driven by the combined effects of deforestation, fire, and climate change. Countries such as India, Cambodia, Vietnam, and Laos are among the most impacted under SSP5-8.5, experiencing accelerated biodiversity loss across highly biodiverse ecosystems. Similarly, the Malay Archipelago is projected to undergo substantial biodiversity declines, reinforcing the urgent need for mitigation strategies that address the compound effects of land-use change and climate change.

Furthermore, countries such as Brazil, Bolivia, Mozambique, Madagascar, India, and Indonesia are expected to experience biodiversity losses over more than 90% of their territories, with some of their highly biodiverse areas suffering a decline of 30%. Even in countries where the impact is geographically restricted, such as Vietnam and Laos, losses are concentrated in highly biodiverse regions, affecting 25% of their land area.

Even under an intermediate socio-economic development scenario with moderate climate mitigation policies (SSP2-4.5), the combined effect of fire, deforestation and climate change will deeply affect megadiverse regions, where not only species richness is high

but also endemism, phylogenetic diversity, and phylogenetic endemism (**Figure 1a**). Additionally, they exhibit a large variation in species composition, thus hosting unique biota. Almost a fifth (19%) of highly biodiverse areas (upper quartile of the biodiversity index) are among those that will suffer the greatest biodiversity losses under SSP2-4.5, with an average 6.16% decline. Under SSP5-8.5, nearly a third of those highly biodiverse areas will suffer the greatest biodiversity losses, with an average 8.22% decline.

The comparative analysis of scenarios underscores the impact of emissions trajectories on biodiversity. Under SSP5-8.5, the percentage of highly biodiverse areas experiencing the greatest losses increases by an additional 10% compared to SSP2-4.5. This increase highlights the implications of insufficient mitigation efforts. While SSP2-4.5 shows a more moderate trajectory, it still results in a relative biodiversity decline of 6.16% on average in highly biodiverse areas, demonstrating that significant losses will occur even under scenarios with moderate climate policies.

Among the megadiverse areas, countries such as Brazil, Bolivia, Mozambique, and Madagascar stand out as the most affected, with biodiversity losses exceeding 30% over more than 90% of their territories under SSP5-8.5. In these regions, the extent and magnitude of losses pose critical challenges for conservation efforts and emphasize the need for region-specific strategies. Additional countries with significant differential losses between scenarios include Paraguay, Guyana, Botswana, and Zambia, where relative biodiversity declines increase sharply under SSP5-8.5 compared to SSP2-4.5.

Figure 1. Biodiversity losses by 2050. a: First Principal Component (PCA) of biodiversity metrics. Warm colours indicate higher values of richness, endemism, phylogenetic diversity, and phylogenetic endemism. b: Percentage loss and c: absolute biodiversity loss under the SSP2 integrated scenario (fire, deforestation, and climate change); d: percentage loss and e: absolute biodiversity loss in the SSP5 integrated scenario; f: differential loss between SSP2 and SSP5 integrated scenarios. The segments in

the legend bars indicate the quartiles in terms of number of cells, thus area, except for b and c that use the same quartiles of d and e, respectively, for comparability's sake. Gray indicates negligible loss values.

Impacts of land-use, climate, and fire (and their interactions)

Our analysis identified eight clusters of countries requiring tailored policy actions to mitigate biodiversity loss, considering the differential impacts of land-use change, climate change, and fire. Countries such as Brazil, Angola, and Mozambique face strong interactions between deforestation, fire, and climate change, indicating that integrated strategies that prioritize forest restoration, fire prevention, and deforestation control are needed.

By contrast, regions like Indonesia and Papua New Guinea exhibit distinct land-use challenges, where Indonesia is heavily affected by deforestation and requires stronger regulations on land conversion, while Papua New Guinea demands proactive conservation measures to safeguard its remaining forests. Additionally, Australia, Sudan, and Niger fall into a category where fire and climate change are the primary drivers of biodiversity loss, requiring robust fire management strategies and climate adaptation policies. These country-specific classifications provide a foundation for targeted conservation planning, ensuring that mitigation efforts are tailored to the dominant environmental stressors in each region. Furthermore, regional-scale analyses reveal that Southeastern Amazon, Sahel, and Southeast Asian forests are hotspots where multiple drivers interact, reinforcing the need for multifaceted conservation strategies that simultaneously address deforestation, climate impacts, and fire risks.

R2. Influence of land tenure as a driver of biodiversity patterns in Brazil

Higher average species richness and endemism in private properties

On average, we found higher biodiversity (both species richness and endemism) estimated per km² of private lands than all other tenure categories, with an average of 329 species potentially found per-property-km² (min/max 0.02-1008 species) (**Fig. 1D**), and an average endemism index value (the sum of species-specific endemism scores) of 73.1 (min/max 0.006-264) (**Fig. 1E**). This is true across Brazil's different biomes, where private lands have higher richness and endemism per unit area from Pantanal to Mata Atlântica and the Amazon.

Figure 2. Mapping of (A) different tenure categories in Brazil, (B) current species richness, and (C) endemism, with the distribution of species richness (D) and endemism (E) per tenure category shown as boxplots (with underlying distributions shown behind as violin plots). The n of each dataset is labelled at

the top of each category, and indicates the resulting dataset post-processing (e.g., we exclude properties <1 km²). Plotted values show mean density of richness (**D**) and endemism (**E**), e.g., the mean species richness per km² in properties across categories. Outlines indicate biomes.

These findings highlight the important role that private properties play for biodiversity conservation in Brazil as they host high numbers of species (including rare species), across all biomes. This may be a surprising finding, as many conservation efforts focus on protected areas (or other areas of conservation), rather than on rural private lands. The finding also contrasts with persistent narratives that assume that biodiversity is highest in protected areas or indigenous lands⁵⁰. We here provide evidence to the contrary, and show that the highest biodiversity per unit area is mostly found under private land ownership. However, this finding should *not* be taken to suggest that other tenure categories host little-no-biodiversity. In fact, all other tenure categories have much larger areas on average (**Table 1**), which may in fact provide crucial contiguous and connective habitat for diverse species. Nonetheless, it is clear that engagement with rural private landowners is also critical for any conservation effort in Brazil.

Vegetation surplus in private lands for current conservation efforts

We also investigated the surplus (and deficit) in native vegetation required to comply with the Forest Code in private lands and rural settlements properties¹. We find that, out of the over 824,000 km² of vegetation surplus in Brazil, 82.6% of this surplus is found in largeholder private lands, with the remaining 10% found in smallholder private lands, and 6.5% in large properties of rural settlements (**Fig. 3A**).

Additionally, we map current species richness weighed by the proportion of each property with vegetation surplus (**Fig. 3B**) to identify areas that currently conserve high numbers of species across biomes (we also mapped endemism which showed similar patterns). Notably, these areas with high richness and vegetation surplus include: large areas of the Pantanal and Pampas, areas across Paraná and São Paulo in the Mata Atlântica, the border region between the Cerrado and Caatinga, and the island of Marajó in Pará (**Fig. 3B**). This indicates that conservation of potentially high numbers of species is happening across all biomes in Brazil – and is not necessarily confined to the Amazon. Moreover, the maintenance of these areas needs to be supported (e.g., via diverse tools or governance mechanisms⁵¹), as any private property with vegetation surplus can still legally deforest.

Vegetation deficit in private lands for future restoration efforts

At the same time, out of the approximately 213,000 km² of total deficit in natural vegetation (deficit in natural vegetation required for either legal reserves or areas of permanent preservation), 83.5% of this deficit stems from large-holding private lands (with approximately 8% owed by smallholder private lands, and another 8% by large-holding rural settlements) (**Fig. 3A**). For these properties, instead of mapping current species richness or endemism, we map the “restoration potential”, i.e., the difference between current biodiversity patterns and a baseline of biodiversity without human-based

¹ We do this by also disaggregating these values between small and large landholders, that is, properties ≥ 4 fiscal modules, because there is evidence indicating that property size influences compliance (Stefanes et al., 2018) and that large properties are responsible for the vast majority of deficit in 2020 (Rajão et al., 2020).

land-use change We weigh this “potential biodiversity” layer by the total deficit of vegetation owed for FC compliance (**Fig. 3C**).

Here, we find that there are areas with at least some restoration potential – and deficit in FC compliance – found throughout all Brazil (**Fig. 3C**, all areas in pink). This suggests that restoration action through fuller compliance of the FC is applicable across almost all private lands in Brazil, and across all biomes. Yet, we also find that the areas with the highest potential gains for biodiversity are found along the border between the Amazon and Cerrado biomes (**Fig. 3C**, darkest areas). These areas should *not* be taken to indicate that fuller compliance would lead to increases in thousands of species. Instead, they indicate that these properties have large areas with vegetation deficit, and that fuller compliance with the FC, a legal requirement, could lead to highly positive outcomes for biodiversity.

Figure 3. Total surplus and deficit in natural vegetation requirements for compliance with the Forest Code across all private lands and rural settlements (> 1 km²), distinguishing between private lands and rural settlements, as well as small and large landholders (properties ≥ 4 FM) (**A**). Note that because smallholder-rural settlements had <1% deficit or surplus in vegetation these are not visibly distinguishable. **B**) maps current mean species richness per property, weighed by the proportion of that property with vegetation surplus for FC compliance. **C**) maps the restoration potential of properties (i.e., potential increases in species richness if loss due to human-driven LUC was recovered), weighed by the amount of total deficit for FC compliance per-property.

Conclusions

This deliverable has demonstrated the value of applying the newly developed biodiversity indicators towards understanding different kinds of drivers of biodiversity loss across the tropical contexts. Moreover, these studies also illustrate how the application of these indicators can be used in identifying the most effective strategies for mitigating future biodiversity loss.

Our first analysis assessed the impacts of environmental drivers – climate change, land-use change, and fire – on biodiversity loss under different future scenarios. The results indicate that significant biodiversity declines are expected across tropical regions, irrespective of different policy interventions. However, the magnitude of loss varies considerably based on the policy scenario, with more optimistic climate policies substantially reducing biodiversity declines, particularly in the Amazon. These findings highlight the critical role of policy decisions in shaping future biodiversity outcomes. Despite the inevitability of some biodiversity loss, proactive climate policies can still make a substantial difference in conserving biodiversity-rich ecosystems.

The second analysis focused on the role of human-driven factors, specifically land tenure, in shaping biodiversity patterns in Brazil. Our spatial overlay analysis revealed that private lands hold higher biodiversity per unit area compared to other tenure categories, such as protected areas and indigenous lands. Additionally, we identified key regions where biodiversity restoration efforts, through compliance with Brazil's Forest Code, could yield the most significant gains. This underscores the need for tailored conservation incentives, both to maintain biodiversity in already well-conserved areas and to encourage restoration in regions where biodiversity has been degraded.

Taken together, these studies illustrate how biodiversity indicators can be operationalized to support conservation decision-making. The findings underscore that effective conservation strategies must account for both environmental and human drivers of biodiversity loss, leveraging policy interventions, land management strategies, and restoration efforts in a targeted manner. The insights gained from this deliverable contribute to a broader research agenda that seeks to integrate biodiversity science with governance and policy frameworks.

Ultimately, as we continue to refine our understanding of biodiversity loss and its drivers, the integration of advanced biodiversity indicators into biodiversity conservation and environmental policies and governance strategies will remain essential in helping mitigate the global biodiversity crisis.

Project outputs achieved

D2.2-4 focused on developing biodiversity indicators which accurately represent multiple dimensions of biodiversity. Here, in **D2.5**, we further fulfill the objective of improving our understanding of the links between trade and biodiversity, as using accurate and appropriate biodiversity indicators is the first, essential, step towards improving this understanding. Here, we demonstrate first use-cases of these improved indicators, both across the tropics and for the specific case of Brazil. Moreover, in answering different questions on both environmental and human drivers of biodiversity change/loss, we contextualize the role of trade impacts on biodiversity within the broader research agenda.

In the first study presented in this deliverable, we isolate the specific effects of land-use change on biodiversity (as compared to climate and fire) – as the impacts of trade are most closely linked to land-use change compared to other environmental factors. Here, we identify that biodiversity in regions like Indonesia and Papua New Guinea might benefit the most from trade-specific policies. This contrasts to other regions, where climate and fire-specific policies may be a higher priority (e.g., Australia, Sudan, Niger), or regions where an integrated strategy is needed (e.g., Brazil, Angola, Mozambique) and effective trade-related policies must be coordinated alongside climate and fire-prevention-focused strategies.

In the second study, we map the distribution of biodiversity across different land tenure categories in Brazil, and identify the crucial role of private lands – i.e., the lands that are most able to lose biodiversity as a result of trade-driven pressure. Here, we can conclude that policies targeting trade-driven biodiversity loss (e.g., the EUDR) are accurately aimed – i.e., at landowners whose land-use choices are most influenced by trade-related market-factors. However, as illustrated in the first study, there is a need for aligned strategies along multiple other factors – as well as consideration of existing local policy infrastructures⁵², in order to effectively target the land-use behavior of these landowners.

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